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MuCoL

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TECHNICAL REPORT

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Abstract:

This report provides a summary of the activities performed by the consortium during the first 24 months of the project. All milestones and deliverables have been submitted in due time, and many results have been published in conferences and journals. The main highlights are the establishment of a complete and coherent set of parameters for the Muon Collider Complex, being updated every year as the design progresses and limitations are overcome, the proposal of a convenient siting option at CERN, and the conceptual design of many critical components (RF cavities and magnet systems).

MuCol Consortium, 2025

For more information on MuCol, its partners and contributors please see <https://mucol.web.cern.ch/>

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Delivery Slip

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1. EXPLANATION OF THE WORK CARRIED OUT AND OVERVIEW OF THE PROGRESS

The MuCol Project has been designed to answer some of the most urgent questions about the feasibility of a Muon Collider at an energy of 10 TeV in the center of mass. The exploration of the potential of such a machine has been recommended by the 2020 update of the European Strategy for Particle Physics (ESPPU), and possible location of a future project could be either CERN or Fermilab in the US. In the future other regions might propose themselves, in particular China.

MuCol has been designed to allow the European community of physicists and engineers to build-up and consolidate the know-how necessary to address all the challenges and be in a solid position, when the time will come, to bid for the construction of such a facility. The challenges of the muon collider come mainly from the short lifetime of muons, that requires the use of very strong electric fields to achieve fast acceleration before they decay, and very strong magnetic fields to reduce the beam size, initially of several cm, down to the few hundred microns that are necessary to achieve the desired values of luminosity in the center of mass of the collisions. Moreover, the decay of muons in the collider produces a large background in the detectors that needs to be minimised and mitigated.

MuCol is organised in 8 workpackages, WP1 dedicated to the coordination of the project, WP2 to physics and detector, then 3 WP for the study of the layouts of the different parts of the collider complex, and lastly 3 WPs dedicated to the main technologies (RadioFrequency, Magnets and cooling cells). In the following we will resume the main results of each WorkPackage.

1.1.1. WP1

The main objectives of this WP are related to the administrative and technical coordination of the project. All Deliverables and Milestones defined in the project have been achieved in time, all the institutes have signed the Grant agreement and the Consortium agreement apart from two candidate associate institutes (Università di Bologna and Brookhaven National Laboratory), for administrative reasons. Their scientists however were allowed to contribute informally, so that there has been no change in the distribution of the tasks.

The main achievements are the establishment of all the documents and tools for collaborative work, including the communication and dissemination plan, the data management plan, areas to store documents in Zenodo ([link](#)) and similar.

From the technical point of view, the main achievement is the establishment and first update of the table of parameters, to ensure that the entire collaboration would be able to work on a coherent set beam characteristics across all the accelerators that constitute the Muon Collider complex, from the source to the collision point.

Finally, in view of the anticipation of the new update of the European Strategy for Particle Physics, advanced from 2026 to 2025, a preliminary layout of a possible implementation at CERN has been studied, showing that it is in principle possible to build such a facility almost entirely on CERN's territory, that simplifies considerably the approval and authorisation process.

Concerning milestones and deliverables, it has been agreed to delay all M&D that in the original plan were falling during holiday periods (summer and Christmas). This is justified by the fact that the start of the project was delayed by two months for administrative reasons, and therefore the original planning of M&D dates was not matching anymore the natural planning of the work. The Dissemination and Exploitation plan had not been requested at the start of the project, but later during the first year, and it was delivered in month 13.

Table 1: Milestones for WPI

Milestone No	Milestone Name	Means of Verification	Due Date (month)	Available at
1	Website Available	Website online	2	https://mucol.web.cern.ch/
2	Kick-off meeting	Indico site	3	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1219912/
3	Tentative parameters available	Database	8	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15110101
4	First annual meeting	Indico site	15	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1325963/
5	Preliminary parameters	Database	20	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13970100

Table 2: Deliverables for WPI

Deliverable No	Deliverable Name	Means of verification	Due Date (months)	Available at
D1.1	Data-management plan	Data Management Plan	8	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10054352
D1.2	Preliminary ESPPU report No. 1	R — Document, report	12	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10723024
	Dissemination and exploitation plan	R — Document, report	13	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15099003
D1.3	Preliminary ESPPU report No. 2	R — Document, report	24	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15099003

1.1.2. WP2

WP2 activities focused on the study of the beam-induced background at center-of-mass energies of 3 TeV and 10 TeV and on producing proof-of-concept detectors designs able to handle the irreducible contribution.

The 3 TeV center-of-mass detector performance has been determined and published [1], while muon collisions at 10 TeV center-of-mass energy are studied in this project for the first time. Performance and physics benchmark determinations are in their preliminary stage, and two detector concepts, denominated MAIA and MUSIC have been proposed and are being studied by independent groups. Preliminary results on the determination of the performance of the two detectors have been presented at a conference [2]

Table 3: Milestones of WP2

Milestone No	Milestone Name	Means of Verification	Due Date (month)	Available at
9	Training on detector design and physics performance tools	Training material	6	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1277924/
10	Workshop on MDI and IR design	Indico site	13	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1353612/
11	Release of simplified detector performance model (DELPHES card or/and similar format)	Model published on the website	20	https://github.com/MuonColliderSoft/Delphes/tree/main and https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14001529

1.1.3. WP3

A preliminary set of parameters for the proton complex was completed and integrated in both the tentative [3] and the preliminary [4] parameters tables. Two options have been studied, a 5 GeV for a 2 MW on target beam), and a 10 GeV (for a 4 MW beam) Superconducting Proton Linac followed by an accumulator ring and a compressor ring, both adapted for the two energies.

WP3 has no deliverables/milestones on its own on the reference period of this report, but contributed to deliverable D1.2 with WP1 on the ESPPU report [5], and to two milestones yet with WP1 on Tentative [3] and Preliminary parameters[4].

1.1.4. WP4

WP4 aims at establishing a layout of the muon production and cooling sections to achieve the required intensity of muons at the beginning of the re-acceleration section and also a reduction in 6D emittance of about 5 orders of magnitude.

Fig. 1: the muon production and cooling section

This section is divided in eight different subsections having different functions as described in Annex 1 (part B) of the grant agreement and shown in fig. 1. Not all sections have been studied yet in details, however starting from a previous study [6] made by the US Muon Accelerator Program ended in 2016, a new layout of the Rectilinear cooling and the final cooling section has been optimised, improving the emittance reduction that is now compatible with the requirement (was still missing a factor 2 in the MAP version). WP4 has been very active with both WP3 to determine the characteristics of the beam impinging on the target, and with WP8 to ensure that the parameters used for the beam dynamics simulations respect the performance expectation of the different components of the cooling cells (magnets, RF cavities and absorbers). Several iterative steps were performed, and more will have to be performed until the end of the study. During the reporting period WP4 had only one deliverable to report on, and no milestones.

Table 4: Deliverables of WP4

Deliverable No	Deliverable Name	Means of verification	Due Date (months)	Available at
D4.1	Development of BDSIM simulation	OTHER	24	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14943349

1.1.5. WP5

WP5 is in charge of defining the layout of the chain of muon accelerators starting at the end of the muon cooling sections and up to the final collider. This required a new study since the US-MAP was targeting a maximum energy of up to 6 TeV in the center of mass. Preliminary layouts however were generated resorting to the scheme of US-MAPS and adapting them to the energy of 10 TeV, and participated to the Machine Detector Interface (MDI) studies with the experiments to ensure an acceptable level of background from decay of muons.

In addition studies to build an impedance model of each machine have been started and are reported in [7].

The work of WP5 has been key to define the tentative [3] and then the preliminary [4] list of parameters published by MuCol. The status of the milestones is the following:

Table 5: Milestones of WP5

Milestone No	Milestone Name	Means of Verification	Due Date (month)	Available at
14	Mini-Workshop on pulsed magnets	Indico site	15	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1388830
15	Tentative design of the interaction region	Optics files	20	https://zenodo.org/records/14000854
16	Tentative optics of the collider ring and pulsed synchrotrons	Optics files	19	https://zenodo.org/records/13847233

WP5 co-organised two workshops, namely milestone M10 and milestone M14.

1.1.6. WP6

The objective of WP6 is to define the RF systems of the various sections of the muon collider complex. The main achievement has been the definition of the RF frequency and the RF gradient to be used in beam dynamics simulations of WP5 for all the machines.

For the collider and the 4 RCS the baseline choice was to use 1.3 GHz cavities as studied by the ILC collaboration[8]. The WP6 team is considering a nominal gradient of 30 MV/m, and is performing some preliminary evaluation of beam loading in the RCS chain.

The muon cooling RF system is very complex for several reasons. Beam dynamics requires to use many different frequencies, and also very high gradients. The team has studied in more details the cavities to be used by WP8, at 704 MHz to define first of all the number of cells that can be fit into the solenoids, taking into account all the ancillaries and the connections for RF, cooling etc... The result is a three-cell cavity for which several options are being considered. Three main challenges are being addressed, namely the nominal achievable gradient to avoid breakdown in the magnetic fields of the solenoids. For the time being studies are being performed at 22.5 MV/m, assuming that beryllium or aluminium windows will separate the cells at their iris. The second challenge is beam loading, that calls for a large increase of the RF power from the klystron for which some mitigations have been proposed and will be studied. Finally, the last challenge is the integration of the cavity inside the tight volume inside the superconducting solenoids. Specific solutions shall have to be studied in the next phase of the project.

Two more topics are under study. The first is a high-power klystron of novel design, able to reach peak power as high as 24 MW with an efficiency of 80%, and. The second is a research on the breakdown rate of RF cavities in magnetic field. A thorough study of the results of previous programmes, including CLIC and the US-MAP ad been performed. In the following period we hope

to have access to test facilities to produce specific data. In particular two test stands are planned, one at INFN-LASA in Milano and one at the SLAC laboratory in the US.

WP6 had no milestones or deliverables foreseen in this period, but was heavily involved in the Milestones 3 and 5, and Deliverables 1.2 and 1.3

1.1.7. WP7

All the magnet systems in the Muon Collider configuration studied within the scope of MuCol have been analysed, in discussion with beam physics, to understand the demands on performance and operating conditions. This has led to a consolidated view of magnet specifications and challenges. A good impression of the challenges at hand can be gained from the summary of magnet development targets reported in Table 6. The values there have evolved beyond initial review of the configuration of US-MAP, to take into account both the changes in beam physics specifications, as well as the progress in conceptual and engineering magnet design. Table 6 is only a simplified view, it lacks many details of the actual machine configuration, and aspects such as field quality, still under discussion. It is nonetheless useful to give a compact view of the exceptional envelope of performance to be achieved.

Table 6: Summary of magnet development targets for the Muon Collider.

	Target, decay and capture	6D cooling	Final cooling	Rapid cycling synchrotron		Collider ring			
Magnet type (-)	Solenoid	Solenoid	Solenoid	NC Dipole	SC Dipole	Dipole	Dipole	Dipole	Quadrupole
SC material options (-)	HTS	HTS/LTS ⁽²⁾	HTS	N/A	HTS	Nb-Ti	Nb ₃ Sn	HTS	HTS
Aperture (mm)	1400	60...800 ⁽³⁾	50	30x100	30x100	160	160	140	140
Length (m)	19	0.08...0.3 ⁽³⁾	0.5...1 ⁽⁴⁾	5	2	4...6 ⁽⁴⁾	4...6 ⁽⁴⁾	4...6 ⁽⁴⁾	3...9 ⁽⁴⁾
Number of magnets (-)	20	2 x 3030	20	7000 ⁽⁶⁾	3000 ⁽⁶⁾	1250 ⁽⁸⁾	1250 ⁽⁸⁾	1250 ⁽⁸⁾	28
Bore Field/Gradient (T)/(T/m)	20	2.6...17.9 ⁽³⁾	> 40	± 1.8 ⁽⁵⁾	10	5	11	14	300
Ramp-rate (T/s)	SS	SS	SS	4200...500 ⁽⁷⁾	SS	SS	SS	SS	SS
Stored energy (MJ)	1400	5...75	4	0.03	3.4	5	20	24	60
Heat load (W/m)	2 ⁽¹⁾	TBD	TBD	1200	5	5	5	10	10
Radiation dose (MGy)	80	TBD	TBD	TBD	TBD	30	30	30	30
Operating temperature (K)	20	4.5...20	4.5	300	20	4.5	4.5	20	4.5...20

As it is clear from above, HTS magnet technology was identified as a crucial technology enabler for a Muon Collider. Having identified the main specifications, concepts and challenges the next step which has been completed was the conceptual design of selected magnets representative of the above challenges. In particular conceptual designs have been developed for:

- Target Solenoid
- 6D cooling solenoid
- Final cooling solenoid
- Hybrid configuration for the RCS (normal conducting plus superconducting dipoles).
- Power system for the fast-switching magnets of the RCS
- Parametric study of the collider dipoles, to consider the margin on the load line, the feasibility of the protection system, mechanical aspects (stress, heating) and finally the cost. A model has been made available to the colleagues of beam dynamics to allow finding optima for the lattice design

WP7 had no own milestones or deliverables but contributed to the establishment of the parameters and co-organised the workshop on pulsed magnets with WP5.

1.1.8. WP8

WP8 is advancing on the design of a cooling cell of a type to be used in the middle of the Rectilinear B section (namely, the B5 type). The choice has been for a cell sufficiently challenging but where the design was deemed feasible within the duration of the project. Past studies had provided only very conceptual designs, without integrating real 3D models of RF cavities and solenoids.

After the choice of the cavity type, made at the end of year 1 [9], the team has performed several iterations to address the difficulties encountered during the design. For instance, following a careful analysis of the required spaces, an interference between the magnets and the RF system was detected, and therefore the multicell cavity has been reduced from 5 cells to 3 cells. A baseline using beryllium or aluminium foils at the iris has been chosen and presently beam loading studies are being performed (by WP6) to confirm that such a configuration can effectively be used. The solenoids have also been designed in detail, considering the space needed for insertion of the dipole coils, for the coil stress management and for the cryostat. Room for the passage of the RF power line and all other connections and services (cryocooler, vacuum, etc...) has also been allocated. The study has been very useful to determine the maximum magnetic field for which mechanical stresses are considered safe. In the last period also a first optimization of the support system, including a thorough floor anchoring system to support lateral forces, has been carried out. Optimisations are still ongoing.

Finally, for the absorber it has been decided to use a solid Lithium Hydride slab, since a liquid hydrogen that would provide better performances would not sustain the deposited power, with peaks in the pressure of evaporated hydrogen that would not be admissible for a reasonable mechanical assembly. A sketch of the proposed cell is in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2: schematic design of the cell being integrated by WP8

Table 7: Deliverables of WP8

Deliverable No	Deliverable Name	Means of verification	Due Date (months)	Available at
D8.1	Presentation of cooling cell conceptual design	OTHER	15	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11402737

1.2. OBJECTIVES

1.2.1. WP1

WP1 had several deliverables and milestones that were all submitted in time. Regular monthly meetings of the MuCol Management meetings were used to assess the progress of each WP, plan general meetings and workshops, follow-up on the fulfilment of the Milestones and Deliverables. When necessary, resources were also discussed. The gender dimension was discussed regularly as the Gender Dimension officer was invited to the meetings, and the Communication and dissemination officer gave regular updates on the papers and talks provided by scientist affiliated to the project.

Cern provided both the Study Leader (D. Schulte) and the Technical Coordinator (R. Losito) who is also the leader of WP1. Main partners of the Study leader were his deputies C. Roger (STFC) for accelerator matters, and D. Lucchesi (UNIPD) for physics and detectors matters.

The main scientific achievement of WP1 is the publication of the two lists of parameters, ensuring the coherence of parameters used across the various machines. The technical coordination concentrated mostly on the hardware designs, performed in WP 6, 7 and 8. Close contact with those

Table 8: Power from the grid for the Muon Collider Stages at CERN and for a Green Field implementation. The higher value for the 3.2 TeV stage collider at CERN is due to the use of low temperature superconductors.

	Unit	CERN 3.2 TeV	CERN 7.6 TeV	Green Field 10 TeV
Proton Driver	MW	16.70	16.70	16.70
6D Cooling	MW	11.76	11.76	11.76
RLAs	MW	10.77	10.77	10.77
RCSs	MW	44.19	108.93	124.68
Collider	MW	10.00	4.10	4.10
General Cooling and Ventilation	MW	20.00	20.00	20.00
Total Power consumption	MW	113.42	172.26	188.01

WP leaders was instrumental to agree on achievable parameters and provide the beam physicists with values to use in their simulations. In several cases experts either at CERN (for instance for cryogenic and vacuum) or in other laboratories were consulted to get advice. Also, regular follow-up of Milestones and deliverables was carried on.

The dissemination of results of the project to the scientific community was overviewed by the Communication and Dissemination Officer, through a peer review process of the papers to be submitted for publication. It is to be noted that the publication and dissemination policy adopted is shared with the larger IMCC collaboration, and the editorial committee is common, to ensure coherence of the publications made in the two contexts. The publication policy is available on the MuCol website. All reports linked to a deliverable or milestone are stored in the MuCol community on Zenodo. CERN provides the Communication and Dissemination Officer that is also the leader of WP1.

The dissemination of results to the general public has been made mostly through social media. The main achievement is the publication of a series of posts on the IMCC LinkedIn profile about achievements and scientists of MuCol. In particular, we published a series of posts about women in MuCol.

Fig. 3: Placement on the CERN site of a Muon Collider complex. After a proton linac, the beam is transported through the existing CERN-SPS to a target area on the Preveessin site, going through cooling and pre-acceleration section then RCS 1 and 2 in the CERN-SPS and RCS 3-4 in the LHC tunnel, and finally a new 10 km tunnel for the collider in red.

For the implementation scenarios it is worth noting that the baseline machine studied by the IMCC is a green field machine that does not assume the existence of previous infrastructure and facilities leaving therefore any option open. CERN intended to develop, towards the end of the project, a scenario for an implementation on its premises using some of the existing facilities and tunnels, to leverage the work performed by MuCol. Given the anticipation of the ESPPU, this task was accelerated in order to be able to propose at least a tentative scenario.

A Muon Collider on the CERN site has been proposed with energies of either 3.2 TeV or 7.6 TeV in the center of mass (see Fig. 3). The 3.2 TeV machine is based on already mature technologies, in particular for the magnets, and therefore is considered feasible to be built and started before 2050. The 7.6 TeV scenario is based in the availability of HTS magnets that can provide 16 T, and therefore will most probably be available only beyond 2050. The selected scenario makes use of the existing SPS and LHC tunnels. This task was mainly performed by CERN. An optimisation of the position of the collider ring is still ongoing and will continue to be pursued. An initial estimate of the power consumption has been made, including all the most power intensive systems (RF, magnets, cryogenics, HVAC etc..) but it is certainly not complete, so it is expected to evolve with the design of the machines. This initial estimation is in Table 8.

1.2.2. WP2

Detailed studies of the 3 TeV detector performances have been performed. The background effects at $\sqrt{s}=3$ TeV have been studied using the interaction region (IR) designed by MAP [10], which

Fig. 4: The MAIA Detector Concept

includes the shielding structure (nozzle). The impact of beam-induced background (BIB) on the detector has been discussed extensively in various meetings and published in several papers with the most recent in [11]. The detector design was adapted to this unique environment, and reconstruction algorithms were developed to mitigate the effects of the irreducible component of the beam-induced background. The results have been presented at conferences and summarized in a publication [1].

Muon collisions at 10 TeV center-of-mass energy are being studied in this project for the first time. The design of the IR has been frozen to produce initial results for the European Strategy for Particle Physics Update (ESPPU). The nozzle configuration, that initially considered a geometry inspired by the work of MAP, was updated to simulate the beam-induced background. The characteristic of such background at $\sqrt{s}=10$ TeV have been discussed in the biweekly Physics & Detector meetings and presented at the conference [12].

Two detector design concepts have been developed, MAIA and MUSIC [2] to optimize 10 TeV center-of-mass muon collisions collection and study them.

Both designs share a similar structure, a cylindrical shape 11.4 m in length with a diameter of 12.8 m. The main detector components are a tracking system, an electromagnetic calorimeter (ECAL), a hadronic calorimeter (HCAL) and a muon system.

Fig. 5: the MUSIC Detector Concept

A superconducting solenoid is also envisioned to provide bending power for the measurement of charged particle momenta within the tracking system. While the tracking system has a similar structure, the MAIA detector has the solenoid just outside the tracking system and before the ECAL, while MUSIC places the solenoid magnet between ECAL and HCAL.

Fig. 6: (left): average occupancy, expressed as the of number of hits per cm^2 , as a function of the tracker system layer due to machine-induced background; (right) the occupancy of the ECAL and HCAL endcap sections, as a function of the longitudinal distance from the interaction point

The determination of performance and physics benchmarks is currently underway, with and they will be published as contributions to the ESPPU. Preliminary results have been presented to a conference [2].

The sub-detectors most affected by the machine-induced background are the tracker and the electromagnetic calorimeter in the case of MUSIC detector. Fig. 6 (left) shows the average occupancy, expressed as the of number of hits per cm^2 , as a function of the tracker system layer due to machine-induced background. To mitigate the impact of this high hit density on track reconstruction, a dedicated tracking algorithm has been developed. Fig. 6 (right) reports the occupancy of the ECAL and HCAL endcap sections, as a function of the longitudinal distance from the interaction point, where it is evident the large amount of energy in the inner layers of ECAL.

The reports submitted to the ESPPU illustrate the performance on almost all the physics objects: tracks, photons, electrons and jets. These results were objectives of the WP due by the end of next year but they have been advanced to contribute to the anticipated timeline of the ESPP update.

1.2.3. WP3

A design, based on the ESS and SPL lattices, for a full energy linac reaching both energies was finalized and a study of the effect of H- stripping on the loss budget of such a machine was completed [2]. The present table of parameters, included in the “preliminary” set of parameters is shown in Table 9:

Table 9: Summary of main parameters for the proton complex for two power options.

Parameter	Unit	Option 1	Option 2
Final Beam Power	MW	2	4
Linac Final energy	GeV	5	10
Repetition rate	Hz	5	
Protons on target	$\times 10^{14}$	5.0	
Accumulated bunch length	Ns	120	
Initial rms energy spread	%	0.025	
Final rms bunch length	Ns	2	
Final rms energy spread	%	1.5	0.6

The main component for the H- stripping losses come from blackbody radiation stripping, which could be circumvented by cooling the vacuum chamber in warm areas and transfer lines below 200 K. Alternatively, the use of a coating that reduces secondary emission can be instigated. This is true for both cases. The stripping as well as the power loss per length as a function of the temperature of the vacuum chamber can be seen in Fig. 7. The intra-beam scattering component is well under control even at higher energies as shown in Fig. 8.

Fig. 7: H^- stripping power loss from Blackbody radiation and a function of the vacuum chamber temperature.

A baseline lattice for the accumulator and compressor for the 5 and 10 GeV cases, based on the studies for the neutrino factory at CERN [3,4] was revised and ported to Xsuite [5]. A series of simulations to verify the lattice behaviour over many turns was launched and indicated no major showstoppers for either option when the beam is accumulated for over about 6000 turns, which corresponds to a linac working at a 5 Hz repetition rate. In the accumulator ring, so far, there is no RF, however, there will be a need for RF barrier buckets to avoid smearing on the bunches over the many turns of accumulation. Currently, the accumulator lengths and number of bunches envisioned for each energy dictate a possible chopping scheme needed for the linac. For the 5 GeV case, the parameters needed, 80 mA and 2.5 ms long pulse, are not too far from what can be achieved today however for the 4 MW case either some R&D is needed or the use of 2 sources in parallel could be an option in order to achieve a 5 ms H^- pulse from the source.

Fig. 8: Intra-beam scattering stripping for a 10 GeV linac. Position zero is the start of the superconducting linac.

The compressor accepts bunches from the accumulator and performs a 90° -bunch rotation in longitudinal phase space. A detailed study of the rotation for both power options was launched and optimization of the bunch length in order to achieve the 2 ns final bunch length, assuming an initial rms momentum spread of 2.5×10^{-4} , was established. For the 5 GeV, a lattice a space-charge driven lattice resonance is excited at the end of rotation causing emittance blow up and needing further study. Fig. 9 shows the initial and final 6D phase space of the bunches before and after compression for the 5 GeV case. For the 10 GeV case the rotation of the bunches is clean and no issues were encountered to reach the 2 ns bunch length so far.

Fig. 9: Example of bunch rotation for the 5 GeV case. (left) initial beam in blue and rotate beam in orange. (right) final bunch length at extraction.

A first look at the transport between ring and target of a 2 ns high current bunch has started. The bunches from the compressor for both energies (and powers) could be transported through a FODO lattice and focused to the specified beam sizes on the target surface without loss of quality and within the specification communicated by WP4 (target).

A detailed R&D plan list for the next 5 to 10 years with key issues for the Proton Complex was layout, with detailed information on intended deliverables and resources needed [5].

1.2.4. WP4

The muon cooling work package aims to establish a baseline for the muon target and cooling system in the light of known technological limits and identify areas where further R&D is required to deliver a satisfactory system conceptual design.

The WP spans from the production target down to the first accelerating linac and is composed of various sections as described in Fig. 1.

We will give here a short description of the results achieved on the various sections. For a more detailed description see the report of D1.3 [7].

Target and Capture section

The target team has designed a baseline radial build for the pion production target, taking into account radiation flux into the surrounding solenoid, heat load on the graphite target itself and appropriate cooling systems for the target and shielding. A 3D FLUKA model for the target area has been constructed and the pion and muon yield through the target system has been assessed. The yield results from simulations are presented in Table 10 assuming a transverse beam sigma of 5 mm, a target rod radius of 15 mm and that all the muon and pions going in the chicane can be captured if their momentum is below 500 MeV/c. The shielding design takes into account the large tolerance to radiation of the selected HTS tape for the superconducting solenoids of the capture section.

Table 10: Yield per unit energy proton beam [$10^{-2}/\text{GeV}/p^+$].

Yield [$10^{-2}/\text{GeV}/p^+$]	Proton beam energy [GeV]							
	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
μ^+	2.8	2.6	2.4	2.3	2.2	2.1	1.9	1.9
μ^-	1.8	1.8	1.8	1.8	1.7	1.7	1.7	1.7
π^+	1.3	1.2	1.1	1.1	1	0.98	0.92	0.9
π^-	0.84	0.81	0.84	0.82	0.83	0.8	0.8	0.81

A major challenge identified is the integration of the dump for the spent proton beam. It is challenging to extract the beam in the high field region and taper owing to the need to maintain a smooth field in this region and so extraction is foreseen in the chicane where fields are relatively lower. The pion and muon beam are deflected here by the solenoid field. The proton beam is much more rigid and so is relatively undeflected. A transition from a high radius solenoid to a low radius solenoid is envisioned to allow space for the protons to leave the beam pipe.

The two charged beams are captured in trains of 21 bunches that are separated and sent into dedicated rectilinear cooling sections.

Rectilinear and final Cooling

New designs for the rectilinear and final cooling have been performed starting from the US-MAP design [6] with the objective to improve the performance and bring it to the values necessary for achieving the target luminosity. The new aspects introduced are:

- Magnets based on the REBCO HTS superconducting material, that can achieve higher fields than the LTS superconductors used in [6].
- Dipoles separated from the solenoids (in [6] it was assumed that dipolar fields would be produced tilting the solenoids). This gives better control of the field intensity and quality.

The rectilinear cooling system is split into two main sections:

- Rectilinear A: operates before bunch merging.
- Rectilinear B: operates after the bunches are merged.

Each section consists of periodic cooling cells including solenoids, dipole magnets, RF cavities, and wedge absorbers made of Lithium Hydride or liquid hydrogen.

A-type cells operate at a low tune (<1), allowing them to accept high-emittance beams. They include a central wedge absorber. B-type cells have a tune between 1 and 2 and offer tighter focusing, suitable for low-emittance beams only.

In beam dynamics simulation RF cavities are modeled as ideal cylindrical 'pillbox' structures with beryllium windows. They operate in TM010 mode for stability in strong magnetic fields. Both standard and π -mode configurations were tested, with similar performance.

RF cavities are modeled as ideal cylindrical 'pillbox' structures with beryllium windows. They operate in TM010 mode for stability in strong magnetic fields. Both standard and π -mode configurations were tested, with similar performance.

After Rectilinear A, 21 bunches are merged into 7 and then combined into a single bunch for further cooling.

Final cooling pushes transverse emittance even lower. It uses ~ 10 short, high-field solenoid cells without dipoles. Two versions (FC-RB8 and FC-RB10) were simulated with RF-Track and G4Beamline, yielding consistent results.

The overall performance estimate of the ionisation cooling system is summarised in Fig. 10. Several challenges have been identified during the study which are listed below.

- Design of the charge separation, bunch merge and reacceleration systems was not progressed owing to a lack of available effort. The target performance was estimated based on simulations performed by MAP.
- The spent proton beam at the target was identified as presenting a significant source of highly penetrating radiation that may cause damage to downstream systems. Design of a proton beam extraction system is ongoing.

Fig. 10: Performance of the ionisation cooling system

- Thermal expansion of liquid hydrogen absorbers under beam heating was identified as a technical challenge. This is viewed as a particular risk for low emittance beams, where energy deposit is more tightly focused, and low energy beams, where energy is deposited in a much shorter distance.

- Beam loading of RF cavities was identified as requiring further study. This is a particular challenge in the rectilinear cooling system where frequencies can be relatively high.
- Integration of highly compact lattices, with very strong fields and high gradient cavities, will be a challenge in the rectilinear cooling system. This is actively studied by the Muon Cooling Cell integration task (WP8).

1.2.5. WP5

WP5 is responsible for defining the layout of the muon acceleration complex from the cooling section to the collider ring. This involves developing new simulations targeting up to 10 TeV center-of-mass energy and optimizing the Machine Detector Interface (MDI) to minimize backgrounds from muon decay.

The main achievements of the WP are:

- Established a preliminary layout for the full accelerator complex up to 10 TeV.
- Achieved >90% muon survival through RLA2 with preserved emittance.
- Developed simulation tools to calculate base parameters for the RCS chain, including RF and magnet requirements.
- Demonstrated feasibility of hybrid RCSs with fast acceleration to 5 TeV.
- Extended the capability of the codes to include intensity effects for both counter-rotating muon bunches.
- Made some progress on the 10 TeV collider design. Despite progress, the momentum acceptance is still insufficient due to non-linear effects and extremely challenging requirements. Explored relaxed betatron functions at the interaction point to significantly increase collider acceptance.
- Validated beam stability through simulations of impedance and collective effects on the entire complex. Results have given some requirements on the injection jitter control.
- Proposed FFA-based alternatives with realistic parameters.
- Established the shielding requirements for superconducting arc magnets.
- Simulated the dose reduction by using movers.
- Calculated the annual effective doses for worst-case scenarios at different distances from the muon decay.
- Developed a tool optimizing collider placement to manage high neutrino fluxes.

1.2.6. WP6

WP6 focuses on developing the RF systems required for muon acceleration, cooling, and collider operation. The work includes cavity design, breakdown mitigation, power source development, and system-level integration. Key studies were performed in collaboration with WP4, WP5, WP8, INFN, CEA, and international labs.

Main achievements are:

- Designed single and multi-cell copper cavities with Be windows for muon cooling.
- Achieved gradient targets and controlled thermal/mechanical stress under magnetic field.
- Performed integrated RF simulations for RCS and matched RF parameters to magnet and optics models.
- Developed high-efficiency klystron design for 24 MW peak power at 352 MHz.
- Laid groundwork for experimental breakdown testing and validation of mitigation techniques.

For the cooling section, we decided to study in details, among the various type of cavities, a 704 MHz copper cavity closed with beryllium windows, that was used also as a basis for the design of the RF structure for WP8. Key objectives included maximizing shunt impedance, minimizing breakdown risk, and enabling magnetic coupling between cells. A three-cell version was optimized, reaching gradients above 20 MV/m with reasonable thermal and mechanical stress. Beam loading and Lorentz force detuning were also analyzed, highlighting the strong impact of beam loading on the required RF power from the source. This aspect will be studied in more details in the next period of the project.

CEA and INFN performed simulations and proposed facilities for testing RF breakdown under strong magnetic fields. Solutions to reduce the Secondary Emission Yield of the surface include beryllium coatings of the surfaces, operation under high-pressure gas (H₂), and low-temperature operation (C³ technology). Two test stands are being built in INFN and one in SLAC to experimentally validate theoretical models and material treatments.

RF system parameters for the Rapid Cycling Synchrotrons (RCS) were integrated in WP5 designs. Simulations revealed transient beam loading challenges and required adjustments to detuning schemes. The goal is to support gradients of 30 MV/m using TESLA-type cavities and realistic power couplers.

Lancaster University led the design of a 352 MHz, 24 MW klystron using a two-stage multi-beam approach. The optimized design uses 30 beamlets with high efficiency (80.4%) and a compact structure. The beam dynamics, cavity optimization, and impedance control were iteratively tuned to meet power and efficiency targets.

1.2.7. WP7

WP7 has undertaken a comprehensive analysis of all magnet systems required for the Muon Collider. The analysis was conducted in collaboration with beam physicists of WPs 3, 4 and 5 to ensure magnet specifications align with performance and operational demands. A key outcome of this work is the identification of High-Temperature Superconductor (HTS) technology as a critical enabler to meet the collider's extreme field and efficiency requirements. The main achievements of WP7 are:

- Developed an optimized HTS solenoid design for the target system with reduced mass and energy (100 tons, 1.4 GJ), cutting power consumption by 90%.
- Proposed engineering rules and numerical optimization tools for 6D cooling solenoids, managing stresses and field integration over 3000 units, in order to allow an easy parametrization for beam dynamics study.

- Designed conceptual 40 T final cooling solenoid with modular pancakes and stress-management for compact, high-performance application.
- Defined resistive and superconducting magnet specs for RCS and HCS systems with novel bipolar/unipolar powering circuits, designed to minimize the power from the grid.
- Completed optimization of multiple resistive dipole geometries to reduce stored energy and manage reactive power efficiently.
- Advanced HTS dipole designs for hybrid synchrotrons, targeting 10T steady fields in challenging thermal environments.
- Initiated collider dipole and quadrupole design using NbTi, Nb₃Sn, and REBCO, with detailed performance maps for 3 TeV and 10 TeV stages.
- Identified critical technology readiness levels (TRLs) across magnet systems to inform future R&D directions.

Solenoids

Significant progress was made in the design of solenoids, beginning with the target solenoid responsible for generating the magnetic field in the muon production and capture region. The newly optimized HTS configuration achieves a peak field of 20 T and demonstrates dramatic improvements over previous designs, with a reduction in stored energy and mass by approximately 50 percent and an order of magnitude decrease in power consumption. For the extensive 6D cooling channel, which consists of nearly 3000 solenoids over one kilometer, a set of engineering rules was developed to manage stresses, operating margins, and field densities. These rules were integrated directly into the beam optics design process, allowing early-stage optimization and more effective solenoid configurations. Additionally, numerical optimization tools were used to refine solenoid geometry based on desired field profiles. The final cooling solenoid, targeting a field of 40 T, presented the most demanding design challenge. A modular pancake coil approach was adopted to address mechanical and electromagnetic loads. This design, with its compact 50 mm bore, also serves as an R&D testbed for broader magnet development.

Accelerator and Powering Systems

The magnet systems for the Rapid Cycling Synchrotrons (RCS) and Hybrid Cycled Synchrotrons (HCS) have been defined with high precision. The resistive dipoles in these systems are specified to reach a peak field of 1.8 T and must cycle at 5 Hz. HTS dipoles are used in hybrid rings to provide a steady-state field of 10 T, allowing the resistive dipoles to swing between positive and negative polarities. This approach reduces the total length of the synchrotron chain. Powering these magnets requires highly efficient reactive power management. Resonant power converters combined with capacitor-based energy storage were selected to achieve the necessary ramping speeds. Magnet geometries, including hourglass, window-frame, and H-type configurations, were extensively optimized using finite element simulations and algorithmic routines. This optimization focused on minimizing stored energy while ensuring field quality and meeting engineering current density constraints.

Collider Magnets

The final stage of the collider requires advanced dipole and quadrupole magnets capable of handling extreme field strengths and large apertures. Initial conceptual designs were developed using a sector coil model that incorporates mechanical stress, protection requirements, and cost considerations. Performance maps were generated for magnets made from NbTi, Nb₃Sn, and REBCO

at different operating temperatures. For a 10 TeV collider, Nb₃Sn dipoles operating at 4.5 K can reach fields of 11 T with an aperture of 158 mm, while REBCO magnets at 20 K can exceed 14 T with a 138 mm aperture. Similarly, inner triplet quadrupoles in the interaction region must achieve gradients of up to 300 T/m with large apertures, posing significant engineering challenges. These requirements exceed those of current projects like HL-LHC and FCC, indicating a need for new technological developments.

Coordination and TRL Mapping

A key aspect of WP7 was the coordination of technology development across different magnet types. A technology readiness level (TRL) mapping was created to evaluate the maturity of each subsystem. This tool helps guide future research and development activities, determining whether further work should focus on small-scale demonstrators or move toward full-scale prototype development. In addition, a strong link has been established with the world of fusion, involving personnel of Fusion for Energy (F4E) in the design of the target solenoid, that has similar characteristics of the toroidal magnet of a Tokamak for fusion.

1.2.8. WP8

WP8 is progressing according to the schedule. The first year a thorough analysis of previous studies for a cooling cell and of its components was performed resulting in the decision to design in details a cooling cell of the Rectilinear B section, this decision was taken to address a design with components performance beyond the present state of the art, but still considered feasible within the time allocated to the project. In particular it was decided to use:

- HTS based solenoids, in order to reach high fields (7T on the beam axis, which means 15-25 T of peak field on the coil) with a large bore
- separated dipoles in order to better control the field,
- a three-cell cavity at 22.5 MV/m
- Lithium Hydride absorbers, as the liquid H₂ technology is not yet mature to be integrated in an eventual prototype to be built after the end of the project.

In parallel, a study for the integration of a test-stand to be used to test RF cavities in high magnetic fields has been developed in collaboration with WP6 and WP7. The similarities with the design of a cooling cell made it an appropriate training to address certain aspects of the design, such as the passage of ancillary elements like cooling lines, RF feeders etc... in a simpler environment before doing it on the more difficult geometry of the cooling cell. Even more important, the exercise for designing the solenoids of the test stand has allowed to carry out an engineering design on the oppositely powered solenoid pairs (which are the basic building blocks of the cooling cell optics). This engineering design has in turn allowed to make the integration of the first cell using correct size and clearance for each component and for the assembly.

Several tradeoffs have been necessary to switch from a conceptual design to a real-world mechanical assembly, in particular the wish of beam physicists to be able to control independently the phase of each cell revealed impossible to implement since there was not enough space for the power couplers. It was therefore decided to implement the power coupler on the center cell, in order to open a passage for the waveguide between the two solenoids. This had as a consequence the fact that the number of cells has to be odd. Three cells were considered the best tradeoff between the

efficiency of the cell, and the possibility to have cells with or without beryllium foils, therefore using a π mode structure. Should the use of beryllium foils be confirmed possible and economically advantageous, a five cell cavity could be considered as the use of foils allow having a π -mode like structure with much shorter length.

The design is progressing well, and an internal review has been organised at the beginning of may 2025 with independent reviewers to make sure no unspotted issue was neglected.

1.3. EXPLANATION OF THE WORK CARRIED OUT PER WP

1.3.1. WP1: Coordination & Communication

Key highlights of **WP1 (Project Coordination and Management)** include:

- On-time submission of all deliverables and milestones,
- Regular management meetings to track progress, plan events, and allocate resources,
- Integration of gender dimension through active participation of the Gender Officer,
- Communication and dissemination updates from the relevant officer.

Table 11

Activity	Status
Submission of all WP1 deliverables and milestones on time	Done
Monthly MuCol Management meetings to track WP progress	Ongoing
Planning of general meetings and workshops	Ongoing
Follow-up on milestones and deliverables during meetings	Ongoing
Discussion of resources when necessary	Ongoing
Regular inclusion of the Gender Dimension officer in meetings	Ongoing
Regular updates from Communication and Dissemination officer	Ongoing

Table 12

	Task 1	Task 2	Task 3	Task 4	Task 5	role
CERN	x	x	x	x	x	Scientific and Technical Coordination, coordination of communication and Dissemination, organisation of workshops, follow-up of milestones and Deliverables.
DESY	X					Contributed to reports and workshops
TUDa	X					Contributed to reports and workshops
UROS	X					Contributed to reports and workshops
CEA	X					Participating to management and coordination
INFN	X					Participating to management and coordination
UMIL	X					Participating to management and coordination

UNIPD	X					Participating to management and coordination
UTWE NTE	X					Contributed to reports and workshops
LIP	X					Contributed to reports and workshops
ESS	X					Participating to management and coordination
UU	X					Contributed to reports and workshops
Imperial	X					Contributed to reports and workshops
UKRI	X					Participating to management and coordination
UWAR	X					Contributed to reports and workshops
ULA	X					Contributed to reports and workshops
SOTON	X					Contributed to reports and workshops
UOS	X					Contributed to reports and workshops
PSI	X					Contributed to reports and workshops
UNIGE	X					Contributed to reports and workshops
SYSU	X					Contributed to reports and workshops
KIT	X					Contributed to reports and workshops
CNRS	X					Contributed to reports and workshops
ENEA	X					Contributed to reports and workshops
UNIBO	X					Contributed to reports and workshops
UNIPV	X					Contributed to reports and workshops
Strathclyde	X					Contributed to reports and workshops
HUD	X					Contributed to reports and workshops

RHLU	X					Contributed to reports and workshops
UOXF	X					Contributed to reports and workshops
ISU	X	X				Provided the Gender Advisor and contributed to reports and workshops.
BNL	X					Contributed to reports and workshops

1.3.1.1. Task 1.1: Study Coordination, CERN

This task features the **leadership and coordination role of CERN in WP1**, focusing on:

- Appointment of the Study Leader and Technical Coordinator,
- Coordination of scientific goals and coherence across different machine systems,
- Publication of two parameter lists as a major milestone,
- Support by deputies focusing on accelerators and detectors.

Table 13

Activity	Status
Appointment of Study Leader (D. Schulte) and Technical Coordinator (R. Losito)	Done
Coordination of scientific goals and activities	Ongoing
Leadership of WP1 by CERN	Done
Publication of two parameter lists for machine coherence	Done
Support from deputies for accelerator (C. Roger) and detector (D. Lucchesi) matters	Done

1.3.1.2. Task 1.2: Technical coordination, CERN

This task highlights **technical coordination activities**, with focus on:

- Support to hardware-focused work packages (WP6, WP7, WP8),
- Collaboration with WP leaders to align parameters with simulation needs,
- Expert consultation (e.g., CERN specialists in cryogenics and vacuum),
- Regular tracking of milestones and deliverables (all submitted on time).
- Coordination of submission of milestone and deliverables.

Table 14

Activity	Status
Technical coordination focused on hardware design WPs (WP6, WP7, WP8)	Ongoing
Close collaboration with WP leaders to define achievable parameters	Ongoing
Provision of parameters to beam physicists for simulations	Ongoing

Consultation with CERN experts (e.g., cryogenics, vacuum) and other labs	Ongoing
Regular monitoring of milestones and deliverables	Ongoing
Timely submission of all milestones and deliverables	Done

1.3.1.3. Task 1.3: Quality Management, CERN

This task concerns **scientific dissemination and communication efforts** of the project. Key points include:

- Ensuring dissemination through peer-reviewed publications,
- Shared publication and editorial policy with IMCC,
- Reports linked to deliverables/milestones archived on Zenodo,
- CERN leads dissemination through its Communication Officer (also WP1 leader).

Table 15

Activity	Status
Establishment of peer review process for project publications	Done
Adoption of publication and dissemination policy shared with IMCC	Done
Use of shared editorial committee with IMCC	Ongoing
Availability of publication policy on MuCol website	Done
Archiving of reports linked to deliverables/milestones on Zenodo	Done
Leadership of dissemination by CERN Communication Officer (also WP1 leader)	Ongoing

1.3.1.4. Task 1.4: Communication and Dissemination, CERN and INFN

This task focuses on **public outreach and social media dissemination**, particularly:

- Led by **CERN and INFN**,
- Use of the **IMCC LinkedIn** profile for sharing MuCol progress and people,
- Special emphasis on **highlighting female scientist in MuCol**.

Table 16

Activity	Status
Use of social media and public presentations for outreach	Ongoing
Management of IMCC LinkedIn profile for MuCol communication	Ongoing
Publication of posts on MuCol achievements and team members	Done
Special series highlighting female scientists in MuCol	Done

1.3.1.5. Task 1.5: Implementation scenarios, CERN

This task concerns the **CERN site implementation study** for the Muon Collider. Key highlights:

- Two proposed scenarios: **3.2 TeV** and **7.6 TeV**, the latter requiring **HTS magnets (16 T)**,
- Use of existing **SPS and LHC tunnels**,
- Initial **power consumption estimates** (RF, magnets, cryogenics, etc.),
- Task led by CERN; **collider ring optimization is ongoing**.

Table 17

Activity	Status
Initial baseline design assuming greenfield implementation	Done
Development of CERN-based implementation scenario leveraging existing tunnels	Done
Acceleration of site study due to ESPPU anticipation	Done
Proposal of 3.2 TeV and 7.6 TeV center-of-mass energy collider scenarios	Done
7.6 TeV scenario based on 16 T HTS magnet availability	Ongoing
Utilization of existing SPS and LHC tunnels in the proposed layout	Done
Ongoing optimization of collider ring placement	Ongoing
Initial estimate of power consumption for key systems (RF, magnets, cryogenics, HVAC)	Done

1.3.2. WP2: Physics & Detector

The activities carried out by each task are described in detail below. The participants are in the following table.

Table 18

	Task 1	Task 2	Task 3	role
CERN	X			Calculation of background and IR configuration
DESY	X	X		Coordination of task 2.2. Scientific and technical coordination of simulation activities, contribution to reports, and organization of workshops.
CEA		X		Participation to reconstruction algorithms development.
INFN	X		X	Coordination of task 2.3. Scientific and technical coordination of simulation activities, contribution to reports, and organization of workshops
UNIPD	X		X	Coordination of task 2.1. Scientific and technical coordination of simulation activities, contribution to reports, and organization of workshops.
LIP		X		Contribution to the development of particle reconstruction algorithms.

UOS		X		Contribution to the development and test of particle reconstruction algorithms. Contribution to workshops organization.
SYSU		X		SYSU was active during the preparation of the proposal, but did not actively participate to the activities. It was however only supposed to provide additional expertise, so no task have suffered.
UNIPV	X	X	X	Contribution to detector simulation, particle reconstruction algorithms development.
ISU	X			Contribution to background study, report writing and workshop organization.

1.3.2.1. Task 2.1 Design of detector configurations at $\sqrt{s}=3$ TeV and $\sqrt{s}=10$ TeV with the optimised interaction regions (UNIPD)

This task focuses on the design of the detectors and their implementation in simulation frameworks. 3 detectors have been proposed:

- A CLIC-like detector for the 3TeV machine
- The Muon System for Interesting Collisions (MUSIC), a detector optimised for 10TeV collisions featuring a tracking system with an extended vertex detector barrel, an electromagnetic calorimeter (ECAL) employing CRILIN technology, a 5 T solenoid positioned between the calorimeters, and a muon detector.
- the Muon Accelerator Instrumented Apparatus (MAIA), that retains the same tracking system as the 3 TeV configuration but incorporates a 5 T solenoid preceding an extended Si-W ECAL, while sharing the same hadronic calorimeter and muon detector as MUSIC.

In the following table we detail the tasks performed.

Table 19

Activity	Status
Implementation of a new tungsten nozzle design for the 10 TeV MDI	Done
Integration of nozzle geometry into detector simulation framework	Done
Evaluation of Beam-Induced Background (BIB) impact on tracking and calorimeters	Done
Proposal of two detector designs for the 10 TeV machine: MUSIC and MAIA	Proposed
Design of MUSIC detector with extended vertex barrel, CRILIN based ECAL, 5 T solenoid, and a muon detector system	Proposed
Design of MAIA detector with Si-W ECAL, 5T solenoid, shared calorimeter and muon detector system	Proposed
Implementation of MUSIC and MAIA designs in simulation framework	Done
Modification of tracking algorithms for new detector geometries	Ongoing
Public release of detector models in Muon Collider repository	Done
Generation of DELPHES card for MUSIC detector performance studies	Done

Use of TrackCovariance module in DELPHES for improved performance modelling	Done
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1.3.2.2. Task 2.1 Design of detector configurations at $\sqrt{s}=3$ TeV and $\sqrt{s}=10$ TeV with the optimised interaction regions (UNIPD)

The focus of this task is on **detector digitisation** and **reconstruction optimisation**, using software tools such as **RealisticCaloDigi**, **ACTStracking**, and **DDMarlinPandora**.

Table 20

Activity	Status
Development and adoption of state-of-the-art detector digitisation software	Ongoing
Extraction of 4D and 5D information from tracking detectors and calorimeters	Ongoing
Survey and integration of RealisticCaloDigi from iLCsoft/key4hep for calorimeter simulation	Done
Validation of RealisticCaloDigi tools in IMCC software stack	Done
Development of a new digitiser for tracking detectors	Ongoing
Performance study of custom tracking digitiser	Ongoing
Optimisation of downstream reconstruction software	Ongoing
Improvement of charged particle trajectory reconstruction with ACTStracking	Ongoing
Enhancement of seed-finding using digitised cluster shape and timing	Ongoing
Calorimeter reconstruction and particle-flow using DDMarlinPandora	Ongoing
Pre-filtering BIB in clustering using adaptive energy thresholds	Ongoing
Performance evaluation within MUSIC and MAIA detector concepts	Ongoing
4D track reconstruction using Quadratic Unconstrained Binary Optimisation (QUBO) formulation	Proposed
Potential use of QUBO for future seeding algorithm improvements	Proposed

1.3.2.3. Task 2.3: Evaluate detector performance at different collision energies by using major physics processes (INFN)

This task concerns the **evaluation of detector performance** (MUSIC and MAIA for 10 TeV, a CLIC-like detector for 3 TeV) in the presence of **Beam Induced Backgrounds**, with a focus on:

- Study of simple physics objects (muons, photons, neutrons),
- Realistic samples including background,
- Benchmark physics channels,
- Sensitivity to Higgs boson production cross sections.

Table 21

Activity	Status
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Development and adoption of state-of-the-art detector digitisation software	Ongoing
Extraction of 4D and 5D information from tracking detectors and calorimeters	Ongoing
Survey and integration of RealisticCaloDigi from iLCsoft/key4hep for calorimeter simulation	Done
Validation of RealisticCaloDigi tools in IMCC software stack	Done
Development of a new digitiser for tracking detectors	Ongoing
Performance study of custom tracking digitiser	Ongoing
Optimisation of downstream reconstruction software	Ongoing
Improvement of charged particle trajectory reconstruction with ACTStracking	Ongoing
Enhancement of seed-finding using digitised cluster shape and timing	Ongoing
Calorimeter reconstruction and particle-flow using DDMarlinPandora	Ongoing
Pre-filtering BIB in clustering using adaptive energy thresholds	Ongoing
Performance evaluation within MUSIC and MAIA detector concepts	Ongoing
4D track reconstruction using QUBO approach	Proposed
Potential use of QUBO for future seeding algorithm improvements	Proposed

1.3.3. WP3: Proton Complex

We have 2 accelerator scientists working at CERN, one at ESS and one at Uppsala University. A postdoc stationed at ESS was hired to work for Task 3.2. WP3 meetings with other stakeholders in UK, US and Japan is held monthly and meeting minutes are available in indico, with institutes also not formally part of WP3 (e.g. STFC and SNS). Active participants are in the following table

Table 22

	Task 1	Task 2	role
CERN	X	X	Given inputs for Task 1 and 2. Deputy chair for the WP. Shared information on LINAC4 performances and possibilities for beam tests
ESS	X	X	Leading the WP and both Tasks. Performed lattice design, simulations and calculations.
UU		X	
UKRI		X	Participate in the monthly meetings and discussions

1.3.3.1. Task 3.1: High power linac (CERN)

A preliminary design for a 2MW (5 GeV) and a 4 MW (10 GeV) H⁻ based linac was developed and the needs in terms of source pulse length and current as well as a preliminary chopping scheme are defined and under further study. A summary of the work completed and still ongoing is shown in the table below:

Table 23

Activity	Status
Definition of the parameter for a high power Linac	done
Design of a Linac (with final energy of 5 and 10 GeV) based on ESS and SPL lattices	done
Define the needs of the Linac front-end in terms of source output current and pulse length	done

1.3.3.2. Task 3.2: Compressor Ring Design (ESS)

A set of self-consistent parameters for the accumulator and compressor rings was combined. An initial set of beam parameters needed on target was agreed with WP4. A series of simulations to verify the space-charge effects during accumulation for both energies was carried out. A summary of the work completed and still ongoing is show in the table below:

Table 24

Activity	Status
Self- consistent set of parameters to be used in the design of a compressor ring	done
Define (with WP4) the parameters of the beam on the Target	done (preliminary)/ongoing
Design of the compressor ring for 5 and 10 GeV final energies	done
Preliminary study of intensity-based effects such as space charge, single-bunch and impedance effects will be carried out for the compressor ring	done (preliminary)/ongoing

1.3.4. WP4: Muon Production & Cooling

WP4 focuses on the muon production and cooling sections and provides specifications for the design of the components (RF, magnets, windows, absorbers) in the cooling line. In addition, it aims at developing software tools to properly simulate the cooling section. Participants are in the following table.

Table 25

	Task 1	Task 2	Task 3	role
CERN	X	X		Collaboration the design of the cooling sections and leading the task for target development

INFN	X			Providing feedback for RF cavities from WP6 and magnets from WP7
UMIL	X			Providing feedback for magnets from WP7 and integration issues for the cooling cell from WP8
Imperial	X		X	Simulations of Rectilinear cooling and development of BDSIM
UKRI	X	X	X	Coordinating the WP, technical supervision of the activities
UWAR		X		FLUKA simulations
ENEA		X		Study of liquid metal targets

1.3.4.1. Task 4.1: Cooling System Development (UKRI)

This task focuses on **cooling lattice design**—specifically the **rectilinear cooling** system and **final cooling stages**, with emphasis on improvements over previous MAP designs and performance trade-offs.

Table 26

Activity	Status
Update and optimisation of rectilinear cooling lattice based on MAP design	Done
Design of two rectilinear cooling channels (Rectilinear A and B)	Done
Performance assessment showing improvement over MAP baseline	Done
Design of final cooling stage for transverse emittance reduction	Ongoing
Evaluation of impact of final cooling on downstream systems and luminosity	Ongoing
Identification of final cooling as key area for decay and absorber losses	Ongoing
Design of two final cooling lattices with different injection points	Ongoing
Performance comparison of final cooling lattices against previous designs	Ongoing

1.3.4.2. Task 4.2: Target System Development (CERN)

This task focused on the **pion production target design**, **FLUKA simulations to determine the muon yield**, and **spent proton beam extraction**

Table 27

Activity	Status
Design of baseline radial build for the pion production target	Done
Assessment of radiation flux into solenoid and heat load on graphite target	Done
Design of appropriate cooling systems for the target and shielding	Done
Development of a 3D FLUKA model for the target area	Done

Assessment of pion and muon yield through the target system	Done
Preliminary estimates of transmission through RF capture system	Preliminary
Study of preliminary concepts for spent proton beam handling	Preliminary
Exploration of beam extraction strategy in the chicane region	Ongoing
Study of solenoid size, magnetic field shape, and shielding for extraction feasibility	Ongoing

1.3.4.3. Task 4.3: Code Development (Imperial)

This task concerns efforts for the **accurate simulation of the muon cooling system**, including work on the **BDSIM code**, field modeling (solenoids, RF cavities, dipoles), and Geant4 material interfaces.

Table 28

Activity	Status
Development of BDSIM code for accurate cooling system modelling	Ongoing
Integration of Geant4 physics processes with matrix-style tracking	Done
Detailed simulation of wedge-shaped absorbers and thin windows	Ongoing
Improvement of superimposed field modelling in compact lattices	Ongoing
Implementation of solenoid field map using elliptical integrals	Done
Accurate solenoid modelling using thin sheet summation technique	Done
Use of TM010 pillbox mode RF cavity model from BDSIM	Done
Development of custom phasing and placement for RF cavities	Done
Implementation of analytical dipole model with Enge expansion	Done
High-order Maxwellian fringe field modelling for dipoles	Done
Implementation of Geant4 material model interfaces for absorbers and windows	Done

1.3.5. WP5: High Energy Complex

Each task organizes separate monthly meetings available in indico with stakeholders also in US. Regular meetings within the different tasks are organized via indico. Participants are in the following table.

Table 29

	Task 1	Task 2	Task 3	Task 4	Task 5	role
CERN	X	X	X	X	X	Deputy of WP5, management of tasks 5.1, 5.3, 5.4, 5.5. Contributed

						to WP5.2. Provided experts in longitudinal beam dynamics, lattice design, interaction region design, MDI, collective effects, radiation studies
UROS		X	X			Longitudinal beam dynamics
CEA		X				Management of WP5, design of the rapid cycling synchrotrons (RCS
UKRI		X				FFA design
UOXF		X				FFA design
BNL		X				RCS and FFA design

1.3.5.1. Task 5.1: Collider design (CERN)

Table 30

Activity	Status
Lattice design of a 10 TeV collider	Design exists but the momentum acceptance is still too small. Ongoing
Scan of the β^* to enlarge the momentum acceptance	Done

1.3.5.2. Task 5.2: Pulsed synchrotron and FFA design (CEA)

Table 31

Activity	Status
Lattice design of the pulsed synchrotrons	Preliminary design exists. Ongoing
Longitudinal dynamics with multi-turn wakefields	Updated with new lattice design
Global parameter optimizer of the acceleration chain	Ongoing
Code amendment to calculate wakefields of counter-propagating beams	Ongoing
Analytical model for vFFAs	Done

1.3.5.3. Task 5.3: Beam dynamics (CERN)

Table 32

Activity	Status
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Impedance models for the chain of pulsed synchrotrons	Includes high-order modes of the RF and magnet chamber designs
Start-to-end tracking simulations in the chain of pulsed synchrotrons	Ongoing
Instability mitigation in the chain of pulsed synchrotrons	Investigated
Impedance models for the collider	Mainly the vacuum chamber
Tracking simulations in the collider	Done
Beam-beam simulations in the collider	Done
Instability mitigation in the collider	Investigated

1.3.5.4. Task 5.4: MDI design and background to experiment (CERN)

Table 33

Activity	Status
Shielding requirements for superconducting arc magnets	Done
Shielding requirements for final focusing magnets	Done

1.3.5.5. Task 5.5: Radiation studies for the accelerators (CERN)

Table 34

Activity	Status
Effective dose from neutrinos produced by decaying muons in collider	Done
Effective dose for different scenarios (including mitigation techniques like wobbling and movers)	Done
Development of optimization tools for the collider positioning	Done
Collider placement optimization	Done
Effective dose from secondary particle showers	Done. Negligible soil activation and groundwater transfer

1.3.6. WP6: RadioFrequency Systems

This work package is currently led by INFN and is supported in some tasks by CEA that provides the deputy WP leader. Apart from the coordination of the work inside the WP, CEA and INFN will ensure proper integration of the work of this work package with the studies done in WP4, WP5 and WP8. Other Participants in this WP are UROS, CERN, ULA and Strathclyde.

The objective of this work package is to assess crucial feasibility issues and technological challenges of the RF systems. The study will concentrate on the two most challenging sections, the Muon Cooling Complex (MCC), and the muon acceleration stage of the High Energy Complex (HEC), for which a baseline concept of most critical RF components will be outlined. Participants are in the following table.

	Task 1	Task 2	Task 3	Task 4	role
CERN	X	X	X	X	Contact with experts, design of 704MHz cavity, contribution to the design of High Efficiency Klystron
UROS	X				Coordination of task 6.1, design of the RF system for collider ring and RCSs
CEA		X	X		Coordination of task 6.3, studies for field emission under magnetic field, design of 704 MHz cavities
INFN	X	X	X	X	Coordination of workpackage 6, coordinator of Task 6.2, Mechanical design of Tuners fo Superconducting cavities, studies for field emission under magnetic field, design of 704 MHz cavities
ULA				X	Coordination of task 6.4, design of High Efficiency Klystrons at 352 MHZ and 704 MHz

1.3.6.1. Task 6.1: Baseline concept of the RF system for acceleration to the High Energy Complex (UROS)

This task focuses on the **RF systems** to be used in the **collider ring** and in the **Rapid Cycling Synchrotrons (RCS)**.

Table 35

Activity	Status
Survey of existing high-frequency SRF cavities at 1.3 GHz and Quantity of Interest (QOI) analysis for the Fundamental Mode (FM) and High Order Mode (HOM couplers	Done
Scaling of one cavity design to different frequencies and number of cells to assess impact	Done
Preliminary power requirement calculations for FM and HOM couplers	Preliminary
Calculation of RF-system parameters for the greenfield study based on ILC TESLA cavity	Preliminary
Integration of RF-system formulas into the RCS parameters Python module	Done
Provision of parameter sets for RCS chain and recirculating linac 2	Done
Use of RCS module for preliminary parameters for Muon Collider in CERN tunnel	Done
Transient beam loading simulation for RCS chain cavity voltage	Done
Identification of the need for an alternative detuning scheme	Identified

1.3.6.2. Task 6.2: Baseline concept of the RF system for the Muon Cooling Complex (CEA and INFN)

This task focuses on the studies for the **RF structures** of the **Ionisation Cooling section**.

Table 36

Activity	Status
Conceptual design of the RF systems for MCC integrating WP4 and WP8 inputs	Ongoing
Investigation of achieving 30 MV/m in 17 T magnetic fields	Ongoing
Study of 704 MHz single-cell cavity, now extended to three-cell configurations	Ongoing
Exploration of magnetic vs electrical coupling between cavities	Ongoing
Assessment of beam loading impact and mitigation strategies	Planned
Conceptual RF design of 704 MHz copper cavity with Be windows	Ongoing
RF-thermo-mechanical analysis of conceptual cavity design	Done
Optimization of cavity geometry to maximize shunt impedance and reduce breakdown risk	Done
Calculation of max electric/magnetic fields, power dissipation, and temperature profile	Done
Assessment of radiation pressure and mechanical stress on Be window	Done
Simulation of mechanical deformation and frequency detuning	Done
Proposal of curved window design to mitigate deformation under Lorentz detuning	Recommended
Design of a three-cell cavity structure with magnetically coupled cells	Done
Optimization of RF power coupler for low power drive (<5 MW)	Done

1.3.6.3. Task 6.3: Break down mitigation studies for cavities of the muon cooling cells (CEA)

This task is focused on understanding and mitigating **RF cavity breakdown in strong magnetic fields**, combining **theoretical studies, simulations, and experimental tests**.

Table 37

Activity	Status
Study of breakdown mechanisms in RF cavities under strong magnetic fields	Ongoing
Extension of theoretical studies with experimental inputs from CLIC and MAP	Ongoing
Proposal of realistic mitigation solutions for high-gradient RF cavity design	Planned
Simulation with CST PIC code on electron trajectories in magnetic fields	Done
Further simulations on electron-surface collision effects	Ongoing

Exploration of initial electron emission as a breakdown trigger hypothesis	Planned
Design of experimental test facility at INFN (operational next February)	Planned
Testing of different materials and surface treatments under 1 T magnetic field	Planned
Design of advanced RF test stand at INFN-Lasa with 3 GHz cavities in 5 T field	Planned
Mockup of 3 GHz RF cavity designed within first 12 months of project	Done
Machining of 3 GHz RF cavity prototype by end of 2025	Planned

1.3.6.4. Task 6.4: Baseline concept of high efficiency and high-power RF sources for the muon collider (ULA)

The aim of this task, led by University of Lancaster, is to provide a **baseline concept** for the **RF sources** needed for the muon collider that will require higher RF power than is currently possible with commercially available sources.

Table 38

Activity	Status
Definition of baseline RF source concept for muon collider	Done
Assessment of power and frequency requirements for muon cooling	Done
Review of commercial klystron designs (e.g. CLIC 1 GHz 20 MW)	Done
Evaluation of scaling challenges to 352 MHz	Done
Study of multi-beam klystron (MBK) concept to reach 24 MW	Ongoing
Analysis of voltage, beamlet current, and tube length trade-offs	Ongoing
Application of two-stage klystron concept to reduce tube length	Ongoing
Scaling of CLIC two-stage MBK using PSP method	Done
Design of 20-beam 16 MW prototype; evaluation of reflected electron issue	Done
Analysis of RF cavity parameters (R/Q, gap length, Q_e , M factor)	Ongoing
Decision to use single-row beam layout for impedance and symmetry	Done
Reoptimization in KlyC for frequency, cavity position, harmonic current	Done
Final MBK design delivering 23.88 MW with 80.4% efficiency	Done

1.3.7. WP7: Magnet Systems

WP7 studies all the magnets of the Muon Collider Complex. One important decision taken from the WP is the use of HTS magnets based on REBCO in order to reach high fields where required. While it is expected that the technology will be mature for solenoids within 5 to 10 years, allowing for mass production of solenoids within 10 years, for dipoles and quadrupoles it is expected that it will take longer.

	Task 1	Task 2	Task 3	Task 4	role
CERN	X	X	X	X	Workpackage leader, Task 1 leader, coordinate all magnet activities and interfaces to beam physics. Task 3 leader, coordinate magnet and powering work for accelerators. Contribute to design and engineering for Tasks 2, 3 and 4 through (i) engineering and demonstration of UHF solenoids, (ii) system optimization of resistive magnet and powering systems for the synchrotrons, (iii) conceptual design of accelerator magnets.
TUDa			X		Design study of resistive magnets to establish losses during ramps and scaling relations suitable for system optimization (2D and 3D modelling)
CEA	X				Participation to communication and coordination activities
INFN		X	X	X	Task 2 and Task 4 leader. Conceptual design activities for all HTS magnets, solenoids and accelerator dipoles for the hybrid synchrotron and collider
UMIL		X		X	Participation in conceptual and engineering design of HTS solenoids and accelerator dipoles for the collider
UTWE NTE			X		Study of HTS options for all-superconducting synchrotrons
SOTON		X			Planned characterization of HTS tape and winding of small-scale, resin-insulated coils to test performance and quench properties of HTS solenoids
PSI		X		X	Material studies for Smart-Insulation in HTS magnets to improve stability and protectability.
UNIGE		X			Development of a new experiment for the electromechanical characterization of HTS tapes. Study of critical surface at low temperature/high field of HTS tapes procured for magnet R&D
UNIBO			X		Conceptual design and optimization of resistive magnets for the synchrotrons, dipoles and quadrupoles
KIT		X			Participation to workshop on HTS tape performance for UHF applications, sharing results of HTS manufacturing trials in KC4.

1.3.7.1. Task 7.2: Solenoids (INFN)

Table 39: Target Solenoid

Activity	Status
Definition of baseline concept for the target solenoid	Done
Design of magnetic field profile for generation and capture	Done
Optimization of solenoid field profile with 20 T peak and 1.5 T exit over 18 m	Done
Ensuring adiabatic expansion of the beam via long field decay (2.5 m)	Done
Design of solenoid using 23 HTS modules	Done
Comparison with US-MAP solenoid configuration	Done
Reduction of solenoid mass to 100 tons (50% of MAP design)	Done
Reduction of stored energy to 1.4 GJ (50% of MAP design)	Done
Reduction of electrical power consumption to 1 MW	Done

Table 40: Cooling channels solenoids

Task	Status
Analysis of US-MAP baseline 6D cooling channel (826 cells, ~970 m, 3000 solenoids)	Done
Evaluation of mechanical stresses, forces, and quench issues in solenoid design	Done
Identification of engineering challenges (e.g. 300 MPa hoop stress, 91 MJ/m ³ energy density)	Done
Development of solenoid design rules incorporating engineering constraints	Done as preliminary round, taken from RFMFTF design; consolidation is on going
Integration of solenoid rules into beam optics design process	Done
Development of numerical optimization tools for solenoid configuration	Done
Application of optimization tools to new 6D optics configuration (3030 solenoids)	Ongoing
Assessment of solenoid parameters: field, bore, length, current density	Ongoing
Identification of tight spacing and RF structure accommodation as future targets	Planned
Incorporation of RF and magnet spacing into next beam optics iteration	Planned

Table 41: Final cooling solenoid

Activity	Status
Definition of 40 T field target and small 50 mm bore for compact R&D testing	Done
Use of non-insulated windings and stress-testing as new technology vehicle	Done
Swift advancement in conceptual and engineering design of 40 T solenoid	Done

Proposal of initial conceptual design using soldered single pancakes and stress plates	Done
Development of radial pre-compression mechanical structure	Ongoing
Engineering development of modular pancake-based solenoid over past 12 months	Ongoing
Design of solenoid with 46 identical pancakes and 3 thicker pairs at both ends	Ongoing

1.3.7.2. Task 7.3: Accelerator magnet and powering systems (CERN)

The largest number and most challenging magnets of the acceleration chain are those in the Rapid Cycled Synchrotrons (RCS) and Hybrid Ramped Synchrotrons (HCS). Among the several configurations studied, we have settled on common specifications for the dipole magnets of all stages, namely:

- Resistive dipoles with 1.8 T peak field and 30 mm (H) x 100 mm (W) rectangular aperture. These dipoles are pulsed with ms time scale at a frequency of 5 Hz. In the RCS they are ramped from injection to peak field (two quadrant), while in HCS they swing from negative to positive peak field (four quadrant).
- Superconducting dipoles with 10 T peak field and the same 30 mm (H) x 100 mm (W) rectangular aperture. These dipoles operate in steady state and provide the field offset for the HCS.

Table 42: Resistive accelerator magnets and powering systems

Activity	Status
Selection of resonant power converters and capacitor-based energy storage for magnet powering	Done
Design of unipolar resonance circuit for RCS (two-quadrant operation)	Done
Design of bipolar resonance circuit for HCS (four-quadrant operation)	Done
Exploration of resistive dipole magnet geometries: hourglass, window-frame, H-type	Done
Optimization to minimize magnet stored energy while meeting 1.8 T field requirement	Done
Development of interactive optimization tool using Matlab and FEMM	Done
Scanning of geometric and electrical variables to minimize cost function	Done
Assessment of field errors and current density effects (10 to 20 A/mm ²)	Done
Ongoing design of quadrupoles for RCS and HCS	Ongoing
Evaluation of AC losses during magnetic field ramps	Ongoing
Analysis of 3D effects on magnetic performance	Ongoing
Global optimization of magnets, power converters, and energy storage systems	Ongoing

Table 43: Superconducting dipoles for the RCS

Task	Status
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Development of superconducting dipole magnets for Hybrid Cycled Synchrotrons (HCS)	Ongoing
Purpose: field offset to enable full swing of resistive dipoles (negative to positive)	Done
Design focus on HTS dipoles operated in gaseous helium (10–20 K)	Ongoing
Target: 10 T steady-state field in 30 mm x 100 mm rectangular aperture	Ongoing
Aperture matching with resistive dipole magnets to ease integration	Done
Use of HTS to ensure large operating margin and reduced power consumption	Ongoing
Design approach accommodates periodic heating from muon decay bursts	Planned
Higher operating temperature simplifies resistive-superconducting transitions	Planned

1.3.7.3. Task 7.4: Collider magnets (INFN)

This task covers the **collider magnet design**, a critical and complex part of the muon collider project. We focused on:

- Analytical evaluation of magnet performance limits,
- A-B (aperture vs. field) and A-G (aperture vs. gradient) trade-offs,
- Material comparisons (NbTi, Nb₃Sn, REBCO),
- Engineering constraints (mechanics, cryogenics, cost),
- Performance targets for dipoles and quadrupoles at various temperatures and energies (3 TeV, 10 TeV).

Table 44

Activity	Status
Identification of collider magnet challenges and integration with beam optics	Done
Analytical evaluation of magnet performance as function of aperture	Done
Definition of A-B and A-G plots for dipoles and quadrupoles (Nb ₃ Sn, REBCO, NbTi)	Done
Inclusion of design constraints: load line margin, protection, mechanics, cost	Done
Comparison of Nb ₃ Sn, REBCO, and NbTi performance at various temperatures	Done
Establishment of performance targets for dipoles (11 T for Nb ₃ Sn @ 4.5 K, 14 T for REBCO @ 20 K)	Done
Evaluation of minimum aperture needs (158 mm @ 4.5 K, 138 mm @ 20 K)	Done
Assessment of stored energy implications for 10 TeV vs. HL-LHC and FCC	Ongoing
Validation of NbTi as candidate for 3 TeV stage dipoles (5 T @ 4.5 K)	Done
Analysis of IR quadrupole gradient/aperture trade-offs for different materials	Done
Identification of largest gradient requirement: 300 T/m with 140 mm aperture	Done
Consideration of quadrupole scaling as a central challenge in IR design	Ongoing

1.3.7.4. Task 7.1: Coordination and communication (CERN)

This task supports coordination, communication, and the definition of future R&D. Key points include:

- Summary of current technology status,
- Identification of major technology gaps based on prior design work,
- Use of Technology Readiness Levels (TRLs) to map maturity across magnet and powering systems,
- Guiding the scope of future R&D from small-scale models (TRL 4–5) to full-scale prototypes (TRL 6+).

Table 45

Activity	Status
Coordination of efforts and communication of results	Ongoing
Summary of current technology status based on design work	Done
Identification of major technology gaps across systems	Done
Definition of R&D planning strategy beyond MuCol	Ongoing
Development of TRL-based framework for magnets and powering systems	Done
Visualization of estimated TRLs for key technologies	Done
Use of TRL mapping to determine appropriate R&D scale (models vs. prototypes)	Ongoing

1.3.8. WP8: Cooling cell integration

WP8 focussed on the selection of the technologies to be used for the first integration exercise. In addition, integration of the RFMFTF (Radio Frequency in Magnetic Field Test Facility), was done. The goal of the RFMFTF is to perform RF tests, but besides providing a background magnetic field to the RF cavity for test, has the ambition to be also the first near-to-final design, pairs of HTS solenoid with characteristics that are very relevant for the design of the actual solenoid pair of each cooling cell. Therefore, the design of the RFMFTF is a very good “training” before starting the more complex integration of the cooling cells. Participants are in the following table:

Table 46

	Task 1	Task 2	Task 3	Task 4	Task 5	role
CERN	x	x	x	x	x	Choice of Absorbers, participation to coordination, provided experts in specific fields such as cryogenics and vacuum.
INFN		x	x	x	x	Provided experts for the design of the solenoids, RF, evaluation of tradeoffs of the performance, participation to integration

UMIL	x	x	x	x	x	Provide experts for: 1) the design of cryo-magnetic systems; 2) the integration concept; 3) engineering design. Provide the coordination of the whole work package, connecting also to WP1, WP4, WP6 and WP7.
Imperial				X		Beam Dynamics studies to find tradeoffs between performance of the cooling channel and performance of the components
UKRI				x		Beam Dynamics studies to find tradeoffs between performance of the cooling channel and performance of the components

1.3.8.1. Absorbers and Windows (CERN)

Activity	Status
Evaluation of LiH and liquid H2 for the requirements of cell B5	Done, selected LiH

1.3.8.2. Solenoids: (UMIL)

Activity	Status
Design of HTS split coil and cryostat	Completed for RFMFTF, with detailed thermal and mechanical analysis; preliminary engineering design for the Stage B5-like cell for the demonstrator nearly completed;
Coil charging transient simulation	Completed for the RFMFTF, using FEM and thermal models; On going for the Stage B5-like for demonstrator.
Cooling strategy optimization	Completed with a feasible operation around 20 K for the RFMFTF (2 cryocoolers); under way for the Stage B5-like cell for the demonstrator

1.3.8.3. RadioFrequency (INFN)

Activity	Status
Selection of a three cell, 704 MHz cavity	done
Complete simulation of single cell	Completed including FEM and thermal models
Simulation of three-cell cavity with Al and Be foils at the iris	Completed with thermomechanical simulations and evaluation of beam loading. Aluminum foils preferred.

1.3.8.4. : Cooling cell performance: (UKRI)

Activity	Status
Iteration to find compromise between field, length of the cell, diameter of solenoids etc...	done

1.3.8.5. : Integration (UMIL)

Activity	Status
Development and testing of RFMFTF	Conceptual design completed; preliminary engineering design nearly completed, pending funding for manufacturing design and construction
Preliminary integration of S5 cooling cell	Completed using scaled-down magnetic field parameters
Evaluation of standalone and lattice configurations	Completed evaluation: standalone is more critical, need s special design to be investigated.
Mitigation of axial forces and heat load with revised layout	Ongoing,: the new inter-cell cryostat concept was introduced and is being refined for assembly; start/end (and stand-alone cell need further investigation)
Selection of optimized coil configuration	Completed, '12 MN 40 mm gap' option chosen
Mechanical feasibility of new coil support	Confirmed within material stress limits
Preparation for demonstrator cell construction	Ongoing, with integration and assembly procedure based on different options

1.4. IMPACT

- The main impact of MuCol has been the formation of a wider community of scientists motivated to study all the aspects of a muon collider complex. The large number of scientists involved not only in MuCol but also in the IMCC as a result of the positive result of MuCol has led to a comprehensive study of the main challenges of the muon collider, and for most of them the community has found principle solutions or indicated possible pathways to solutions, to be pursued through a yet to be founded R&D programme. This resulted in the possibility to submit a solid proposal to the ESPPU process [13], which will give recommendations to CERN Council on the next machine to be built, and on the R&D programmes to be setup or continued.
- The establishment of an implementation scenario at CERN showed that it is in principle possible to exploit already existing tunnels therefore reducing considerably the CO₂ footprint of construction of the facility. For other facility, the tunnels to be excavated count for 30% to 50% of the total. In our scenario, civil engineering will contribute with around 10% of the total. Moreover, even if not yet complete, the power estimate shows that it is possible to build

a machine with a scientific reach equivalent for many physics channels to the FCC, with a much-reduced power consumption.

- The MuCol magnet team has established many contacts with communities interested to the development of solenoids based on HTS, and in particular with the world of fusion. CERN is now setting up a new collaboration, involving many actors, public and private, involved in fusion research to fund the construction of a prototype of the target solenoid, which has many characteristics in common with solenoids used by modern tokamaks.
- A new development for detectors has been studied thanks to the work of WP2. During the presentation of electron, photon and jet reconstruction performance by using a silicon-tungsten based calorimeter, experts of these detector systems questioned if a different configuration with enhanced time capabilities and cheaper cost could be used. Experts on calorimeter devices proposed CRILIN, CRystal calorImeter with Longitudinal Information [14]. A possible configuration was studied with the $\sqrt{s}=3$ TeV and found very well performing. Several test beams have been proposed and funded by INFN. The results, published in [15] are very encouraging. The MUSIC detector for $\sqrt{s}=10$ TeV uses this technology as default and it could be exploited also in e^+e^- experiments.
- Still on detector design, MuCol has made major contributions to the generic software stack dedicated to future colliders (key4hep). The decision to update the IMCC software to rely on the key4hep stack allowed to more widely distribute the algorithms developed within MuCol to the general high-energy physics community. In particular, key contributions were made in the development of tracking software ([ACTSTracking](#)) and the development of workflows for the synthesization of [docker images](#) of software releases for distribution and long-term preservation, which are now being picked up as standards for the collider physics community.

1.5. UPDATES OF THE PLAN FOR EXPLOITATION AND DISSEMINATION OF RESULTS (IF APPLICABLE)

No updates are foreseen.

2. EXPLOITATION PRIMARILY IN NON-ASSOCIATED THIRD COUNTRIES (IF APPLICABLE)

Not applicable

3. OPEN SCIENCE

All reports linked to a milestone or deliverable are stored in Zenodo. For deliverable where a dataset was expected (such as a layout of a machine), we published a report providing a description of the

problem, of the tool used to produce the result and the link to download the data, typically from github.com. All publications are open access.

The activities conducted in **WP2** are documented here <https://mcd-wiki.web.cern.ch/>, MuonColliderDetector page. The group has produced software releases documented in the page linked above. The software is open, distributed via github (<https://github.com/MuonColliderSoft>)

Tutorials for newcomers have been prepared and executed in different locations, the material is available to anybody, and they are linked on the MuonColliderDetector page (Milestone N.9).

The workshop foreseen in collaboration with WP5 has been held at CERN, <https://indico.cern.ch/event/1402725/overview> (Milestone 10).

The $\sqrt{s}=10$ TeV detector DELPHES card (Milestone 11) is publicly available on github (<https://github.com/MuonColliderSoft/Delphes/tree/main>) and its description is published on zenodo <https://zenodo.org/records/14001529>.

The repository of all layouts for **WP3** are in: <https://gitlab.esss.lu.se/ess-bp/mucol-lattice>

The repository for layouts used in WP4 are in: <https://github.com/orgs/MuonCollider-WG4/>

The repository for layouts and impedance models used in WP5 are in:

- https://gitlab.cern.ch/acc-models/acc-models-mc/-/tree/master/high_energy_complex for the high-energy complex.
- <https://gitlab.cern.ch/acc-models/acc-models-mc/-/tree/master/collider> for the collider.
- <https://muc-impedance.docs.cern.ch/> for the impedance model, including the documentation pages, the impedance model data presented in interactive plots, and the related data.

For WP 6 to 8, the level of design is still at a conceptual phase, and therefore in constant evolution.

4. DEVIATIONS FROM ANNEX 1 AND ANNEX 2 (IF APPLICABLE)

4.1. TASKS/OBJECTIVES

All the objectives of the project are on track, and some of them have actually progressed faster than expected thanks to the positive impact that the approval of MuCol had on the physics community. In fact, many scientists decided to work on the muon collider through the IMCC collaboration that gave more resources than expected. In particular, the site implementation at CERN was expected to be performed in the last year of MuCol, but it was decided to advance it to submit a solid proposal to the ESPPU.

4.2. USE OF RESOURCES

The deviations from the linear expenditure for reporting period no. 1, which represents 50% of the total project duration, are explained below.

Overall, the project expenditure is in line with the planned budget: after period 1 (50% of the total duration), 51.92% of the planned costs and 47.18% of the planned person months have been spent.

In the following, the individual deviations from the linear expenditure are explained by the partners concerned:

Beneficiary 2 - DESY: no costs have been declared at this stage, as a student will be employed to work on the project during reporting period 2; at this stage, the work on the project has been carried out with free PMs.

Beneficiary 4 - UROS: The beneficiary will be able to complete the project even though the EU funds have already been used up. In the original proposal, UROS planned to fund a researcher with EU funds in 2024. As before, the beneficiary will continue to provide matching funds. This will consist of personnel supported by the budget, e.g. the scientist in charge with a certain number of hours, and mainly a Gentner student who will focus entirely on UROS's tasks in the MuCol project. The beneficiary expects to complete the project from now on, on the basis of matching funds.

Beneficiary 5 - CEA: personnel costs reported partly as unit costs and partly as actual costs: in order to be consistent with CEA's usual practice, CEA charged permanent staff as unit costs and non-permanent staff as actual costs. When the Grant Agreement budget was initially prepared, all personnel costs were categorised as actual costs, as the split between actual and unit cost allocations was not known at the time.

Beneficiary 6 INFN has considerably higher average personnel costs than expected as the INFN average cost salary was assumed to hire new post-docs to contribute to the project. In this first period mainly staff personnel carried out the activities, and their higher average salaries accounts for the difference. Moreover, INFN is already on the path to match the required total number of PM by the end of the project.

Beneficiary 8- UNIPD: The beneficiary had initially planned to declare only post-docs but given the difficulties and constraints in the recruitment process and the need to carry out the planned tasks, an increase in personnel costs had to be declared in order to carry out the planned tasks. A higher number of hours was declared to carry out the work and prepare the documents to be submitted to the ESPPU. From now on, the beneficiary will declare fewer hours. No additional funding will be requested.

Beneficiary 9 – UTWENTE: personnel costs were reported as unit costs, UTWENTE used Average Personnel Costs (unit cost according to usual cost accounting practices). Concerning the exact nature and project use of the equipment titled TCO54243 Bovenplaat Jorick and TCO54256 Shrinkfit rings on coil. The two items were manufactured by TCO for the purpose of

testing of HighTemperature Superconductor (HTS) technology; the top plate (TCO54243) is an essential part required to carry out testing and the shrink fit rings (TCO054256) are part of the test coils.

Claim for two items in the category “Internally invoiced goods and Services”: TCO54243 Bovenplaat Jorick (€895.84) and TCO54256 Shrinkfit rings on coil (€576.93): The beneficiary herewith confirm that the costs comply with the eligibility conditions set out in Article 6.2.D.2 of the Grant Agreement and have been correctly allocated in the Financial Statement. The Financial Statement has been adjusted to reflect that these costs for Internally invoiced goods were not foreseen in Annex 1. The explanation is as follows: The two items were manufactured by TCO for the purpose of testing HighTemperature Superconductor (HTS) technology: The top plate (TCO54243) is an essential part required to carry out testing. The shrink fit rings (TCO054256) are part of the test coils

Beneficiary 12 – UU: No personnel costs reported because the original plan was for ESS and UU to collaborate on WP3 through a postdoc, supervised jointly. This postdoc has accepted another positioned, which hindered her from spending time at UU. Therefore, no expenses have been declared so far at UU. However, starting from May 2025 the beneficiary has recruited another person who will be working on MuCol WP3, so in the next reporting period they will declare costs.

4.2.1. Unforeseen subcontracting (if applicable)

4.2.2. Unforeseen use of in-kind contributions

5. REFERENCES

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